

INTERPRETATION OF SINGLE-LETTER AUXILIARY WORDS IN "MIFTAHU-L-ULUM"

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Akmalkhan Akmalkhonov

International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan

Uzbek language and classical oriental literature

senior teacher of the department, philological sciences

Doctor of Philosophy, Ph.D

Abstract: *The work "Miftahu-l-ulum" differs from other sources of the field in that it has a different method of interpretation. It can be felt in each of them that Abu Ya'qub Sakkaki wrote the subject of the work based on a special memory. Taking into account the characteristics of the auxiliary word group, Sakkaki wrote this word group in detail based on a special method. It can also be seen from the fact that the auxiliary words are divided into groups. The category of auxiliary words is covered by Sakkakiy under the topic "?????? - types of auxiliary words". First, in this topic, auxiliary words were divided into two groups according to their syntactic features, and according to their structure, which category they can come with, they were further divided into groups, and each of them was described separately. Based on his scientific conclusions, Sakkaki divided the groups of auxiliary words in the Arabic language into six groups and named each of them taking into account their syntactic features. Groups of auxiliary word groups divided by Sakkaki: Auxiliary words that bring the next word in the accusative agreement (komakchi)(ħrwf aljr), auxiliary words that bring word groups independent of the verb in the accusative agreement (?????? ??????), auxiliary words in the conditional mood (???????? ??????????), auxiliary words in the imperative mood (?????? ??????), words in the subjunctive agreement, then in the main agreement (?? ?????? ?? ?????? ?? ??????), in the main agreement, and then in the subjunctive agreement (?? ?????? ?? ?????? ?? ?????????). When dividing the words in the auxiliary category into types according to the structure, the author uses the number of letters as a criterion. The first of the group, divided according to the structure, is auxiliary words consisting of one letter. He described the syntactic features of such auxiliary words as well as the semantic differences.*

Key words: *Abu Ya'qub Sakkaki, "Miftahu-l-ulum", nahv, auxiliary, loading, connecting, independent word group, auxiliary word group, agreement category.*

It can be said that the group of auxiliary words is relatively simple from the morphological point of view, because it is not formed from other groups. In syntactic processes, their functions are manifested in connection with the next word, and this feature does not differ from the scope of noun and verb groups. According to the syntactic function, the letter is connected with the noun and the verb, and as a result of the

connection, syntactic changes occur in both categories. Also, the letter is semantically multitasking and expresses different meanings depending on the context. (The auxiliary word group is called "harf" in Arabic, the article uses both terms interchangeably).

Taking into account the above specific aspects, Sakkoki explains the letter group in detail based on a special method. It can also be seen from the fact that he divided the letters into groups. In this regard, the scientist argues under the topic "الاحرف ال انواع" - types of auxiliary words" [1: 39a-40a].

Sakkoki begins the discussion by saying, "If we dwell on auxiliary words (letters), they can introduce the word after them in raf', nasb, jar and jazm" [1: 39a]. According to the function of the letter, it comes before nouns and verbs. It does not come after the word it is linked to. Since these letters are a separate group and have different meanings, the scientist said, "They can be sorted by grouping them as follows. Letters are divided into two groups::

1. A letter causing a syntactic change (ال عامل الحرف)
2. A letter that does not cause any syntactic change (ال عامل غير الحرف)," he wrote [1: 39a].

Sakkoki divided them into the first two groups according to their participation in the syntactic process. One of the scholars of our time, Mustafa Ghalayani, while keeping this order, divides it into two aspects and calls a letter that does not perform a syntactic function not as ال عاملة غير like Sakkoki, but as عطل حرف - (inactive letter) [13: 689].

Abulqasim Abdurahman Suhaili, one of the famous linguists, said: "Each of the letters actually performs a syntactic task. There is no letter in the sentence that does not perform any function. He is performing a certain task", and giving an example of the sentence hl qam zyd - (Did Zayd stand?), he emphasizes that hl comes in the function of expressing the meaning of question in the sentence [7: 59].

Contrary to other scholars, Sakkoki divides the letter (ال عامل حرفال) that performs a syntactic function into the following types: "The letter (ال عامل الحرف) that causes a syntactic change is divided into two types. One: a letter that causes a syntactic change; the second: a letter that causes two syntactic changes," he wrote [1: 39a]. This distribution was divided according to its activity in the syntactic process.

Mahmoud Zamakhshari emphasizes that a letter does not have a meaning without being associated with a word other than itself, and states that letters carry the meanings of verbs to nouns. He divides them into three groups. One: the one who keeps the characteristic of letters (lāzım llħrfyē); the second: the one that comes as a name and a letter (kəḩn asmā wħrfā); the third: the one that comes as a verb and a letter (qān f'la wħrfā) is counted [17: 239].

The above distribution of Mahmud Zamakhshari is related to which category the letters belong to or from which category they originate.

Saccocus focused on the letters performing a task, defining them as: the letter that causes a syntactic change in the names; the letter that causes syntactic change in verbs

was distributed [1: 39a]. This division was made taking into account word groups, and most of the letters characteristic of nouns do not accompany verbs.

According to the opinion of the scientist, the letters characterized by nouns and verbs are divided into the following groups: jar "الجر حرف" (which changes the end of the name to kasra [i] or fatha [a]) letter (Basra linguistics so called in his school, see: 12: 175); Nosiba "النا صب حرف" (changing the end of the name to fatha [a]) letter. The letter that causes syntactic change in verbs is also divided into two groups. One: jazm "الجازم حرف" (which changes the end of the verb to silence) letter; the second: the letter "النا صب حرف" (which changes the end of the verb to fatha [a]) [1: 39a]. (In the following places, the words jar, nasb, raf' and jazm are used. These concepts represent agreement when referring to nouns, and inclination when referring to verbs. In this context, raf'-head agreement and message like; genitive case and desire case; subjunctive case case; case of case. This is also not considered equivalent equivalent. These words are used because they match in many respects).

The letter (النا صب حرف) that brings the noun in the accusative case and the letter (النا صب حرف) that requires the verb to be in the mood of desire are not considered to be the same letter.

About the letters that cause two syntactic changes at the same time: "The letters that cause two syntactic changes are divided into two groups, one: the letter that changes nasb to raf; the second: a letter that changes after raf' to nasb," said Sakkokiy [1: 39a].

Ibn Ya'ish connected with the name according to the position of the letters, giving it only the meaning of certainty (alkatb-known writer), connected with the verb, giving an additional meaning (qd divides into ktb-written). The letter qd gives an additional meaning to the verb. The third one divides it into letters such as أ، هل، which only join the sentence (كاتب أنت - are you a writer?) [4: 450].

This division of Ibn Ya'ish is based on the fact that the letters have a morphological effect on the word and a semantic change in the meaning.

Among these letters, the most commonly used are auxiliaries (الجر حروف) that are added to these nouns and require the accusative case to change it to a kasra or a fatha instead of a kasra. In this chapter, selected auxiliaries (الجر حروف) from the above types will be highlighted (instead of the combination "harfi jar" during the debate, "harf", "auxiliary word", "auxiliary" was used).

Such auxiliaries can only be connected with a noun, and only a demonstrative pronoun can be added between the noun and the auxiliary, in other cases no word can come between the noun and the auxiliary.

الجر حروف - letters that change the end of the word to a kasra [i], fatha [a] in double-consonant words (المن صرف غير)

This type of letters is called "accentive letter" (ḥrf aljir), "additive letter" (ḥrf alēdafa), "adjective letter" (ḥrf alšfē), "accusative letter" (ḥrf alkhfd). Calling "additive letter" (حرف الإضافة) and "adjective letter" (الصفة حرف) is characteristic of the Kufa school of

linguistics [14: 165]. Sakkoki's presentation of these letters in the form of ḥrwf aljr shows that he is a supporter of the representatives of the Basra school of linguistics.

Saccocius spoke about the number of jar letters and said about them: "The number of these is nineteen, and only the names come together."

There is a difference in the number of this type of auxiliary words, Mahmoud Zamakhshari [17: 239] and seventeen, Ibn Hisham Ansari [6: 250], Mustafa Ghalayani [13: 613] and Hasan Abbas [10 : 25] who said twenty.

Sakkoki divides these auxiliary words into two types depending on the number of letters in them, and calls those consisting of one letter "simple" (بسيط), and those with more than one letter as "complex" (مركب) [1: 39a]. Although this division seems simple, it is of great importance in spelling and pronunciation. For example: الله عبد آذ تم (Are you God's servants?).

In the simple (consisting of one letter) jar letters, the scientist introduces the following six words: ك - (-like, like), ل - (-of, for), ب - (with, by means of), ت- (tā representing oath), م- (mīm representing oath), و- (vāv representing oath) [1: 39b].

Unlike the rest of the scholars, Sakkoki said that these auxiliary words are nineteen, with the introduction of the letter م - (mīm, which represents an oath). This auxiliary word was left out of the attention of other scientists.

ال لام (الخاصة تصاحص لام) - belonging, this letter expressing the meanings of ownership is added to the word that is semantically related to it. As an example, Sakkoki cites the following examples: ل زيد مال - (the property belongs to Zayd); ل ل فرس الجمل - (it belongs to the horse) [MU, 39b]. This letter has different meanings depending on the place of use. Even if it is used in an additive form, it is considered to contain a certain meaning of emphasis. It is often used in verses of the Qur'an and poetry. Usually, this letter means "relevance", "belonging", and in the structure of the verb, it expresses the meaning of purpose, cause. Emphasis is used in both categories.

In Arabic, the expression of an oath covers certain syntactic rules, and there are letters that express it. One such letter is ال - ("tā denoting an oath"). About the syntactic features of this letter, Sakkoki: ال - ("tā expressing oath") is used with proper nouns and expresses the meaning of oath. It is added only to the name of Allah. Akhflash narrated trb al-kabah - "Oath by the Lord of the Ka'bah" [1: 39b].

Sakkoki and other scholars cited ال - ("swearing tā") as part of this type of letter because the word it was added to appeared in the accusative as altā' - (swearing tā).

One of the letters added to the semantically connected word is ال با - ("with, through"), and ال با - ("with, through") is used to connect words is used, for example: باه - there is a fault. This letter is an oath, atf (combined participle), in auxiliary meanings, عن - ("about, from"), في - ("at, in"), م' - ("with, along with") ma also represents names. For example: به سالت - (I asked him); فلان بلبلد - (in such and such country); ال فر به ثياب لم يه دخلت - (I entered him in traveling clothes)," Sakkoki said [1: 39b].

The last two auxiliary words, consisting of one letter, are used to express an oath and bring the word to which it is connected in the accusative case. About these Sakkoki: الميم - ("mīm denoting an oath") is used for an oath. لأفعلن بالله م - I swear to Allah, I will definitely do it. This letter is also used only with the name of Allah. perhaps it is a contraction of the word بين م - "oath", he said about the latter, الو - (vāv representing oath) is used for oath and does not come with pronouns" [1: 39b].

Although it is brief, this definition, which covers important rules, differs from the definitions of other scholars. "mīm" representing an oath is used as a "kasra", and according to the scientist, it is considered the second letter of the word بين م - (oath), and the remaining letters are omitted. This view of the scientist is close to the views of the school of Kufa, and supporters of this school also support the opinion that the word mīm denoting an oath is derived from the plural form of أيمن م - (oaths). Mahmud Zamakhshari said that this word was derived from the word ايم م - (oath) and wrote its forms with kasra and dhamma. And some scholars say that it is "mîm" which is replaced by "vāv" which means oath. Because these two letters are close to each other instead of being formed [4: 493-495].

Sakkoki's quotation of this letter with a kasra is given in this form because the letter b- (with, by means of) is also a kasra when it comes alone [1: 39b]. The fact that the remaining letters of the "mīm" representing the oath were so shortened and dropped caused different views. It can be said that one of the reasons for this is that it is used a lot.

Although the forms given by Sakkoki or Mahmud Zamakhshari are different, they express the meaning of "swear".

Auxiliary words consisting of one letter can be combined with semantically related words, and some of them can be written separately. If "mīm" representing an oath is not added to semantically related words because it is considered a component of another word, "vāv" in this function is not added because it is one of two letters is written.

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